

COBLATION VERSUS BIPOLAR ELECTROCAUTERY TONSILLECTOMY:
A COMPARATIVE STUDY IN CHILDREN

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Abstract

Objective: To assess the mean operating time, per operative blood loss and post operative complications in Coblation tonsillectomy and Bipolar Electrocautery tonsillectomy techniques. To compare the two techniques of tonsillectomies, Coblation versus Bipolar Electrocautery, for suitability in children. To assess the rate of post operative haemorrhage in Coblation versus Bipolar electrocautery tonsillectomy. To assess the prolonged post-op pain in both procedures.

Study design: Prospective comparative study

Place and duration of study: Combined Military Hospital, Kharian Cantt from 1st February 2023 to 31st January 2024.

Methodology: Two groups named as Group A and Group B. A total of 60 children aged 4–15 years were randomly allocated into two equal groups: **Group A** (Coblation tonsillectomy) and **Group B** (Bipolar Electrocautery tonsillectomy). Operative time, intraoperative blood loss, postoperative pain (assessed with Wong-Baker FACES Pain Rating Scale), and postoperative complications were recorded. Data were analyzed using **SPSS 29.0**

Results: The mean operative time was significantly shorter in Group B **15.45 ± 0.48 min** compared to Group A **20.78 ± 1.14 min**, $p < 0.05$. Intraoperative blood loss was slightly lower in Group A (**6.48 ± 0.67 ml**) than Group B (**7.47 ± 0.42 ml**), though not statistically significant. Mean postoperative pain scores were significantly lower in Group A (**2.9 ± 0.76**) than Group B (**3.8 ± 0.95**, $p < 0.05$). No postoperative hemorrhage occurred in Group A, whereas two cases (**6.7%**) of secondary hemorrhage were reported in Group B

Conclusion: It is concluded that Coblation and Bipolar Electrocautery Tonsillectomy both are beneficial in children. Electrocautery tonsillectomy has a mean less operative time

INTRODUCTION

Tonsillectomy is most commonly performed in ENT for pediatric age group.¹ Healthcare providers recommend this procedure for two major reasons; a) to treat breathing disorders affecting sleep and b) to decrease incidents of frequent infections.² Although this procedure dates back to pre-historic times approximately 1000 BC, certain scriptures outlining fingernail dissection.³ Total tonsillectomy was first described by Cornelius Celsius in the 1st century AD. Snare tonsillectomy was introduced by Galen which remained the technique till 400 years even till date it is widely employed by many ENT surgeons. Electrocautery technique for tonsillectomy gained popularity in 1950s.⁴

In this technological era, new and improved antibiotics have evolved guidelines for surgical intervention. Indications for tonsillectomy have also evolved with more inclination for treatment of sleep related breathing disorders (sleep apnoea).⁵ Now there are many surgical techniques for performing tonsillectomy as mentioned that tonsillectomy is used to address recurring tonsillitis. This procedure reduces the frequency of throat infections just to improve breathing in case of obstruction.⁵ The various techniques used for this procedure include bipolar diathermy and electrocautery tonsillectomy, blunt cold steel dissection, and Coblation tonsillectomy.⁶ There are two techniques that are majorly used in children that is Coblation and Bipolar electrocautery tonsillectomy.⁷ It is noted that these procedures are associated with less postoperative pain.¹ It takes maximum 1-2 weeks to recover by temporary changes in the voice. It is noted that Bipolar electrocautery tonsillectomy and Coblation tonsillectomy are considered having low risks of primary and secondary haemorrhage.⁴ Coblation tonsillectomy uses a bipolar system involving radiofrequency which is known as coblation. This technique uses radiofrequency energy combined with a saline solution. The purpose behind this collaboration is to create a plasma field that appears helpful to dissolve tissues at low temperature. It is noted that coblation tonsillectomy is less painful by causing

less bleeding.^{1,4} On the other hand, bipolar electrocautery tonsillectomy is commonly done in children by using bipolar electrocautery technology. It is noted that electrical energy is used in this technique that works by cutting tissues and achieve haemostasis simultaneously. It allows two currents to pass through the tissues by placing two electrodes close to each other.⁷ It helps to effect larger area at local temperature 400 C to 600 C. Bipolar electrocautery tonsillectomy firstly removes the tonsils by the device that cut tissues to minimize the bleeding.⁸ The same device produces complete haemostasis. In children, it is noted that these two techniques are valid to cure recurrent tonsillitis.

The rationale of this study is the comparison between two techniques of tonsillectomy by coblation method and bipolar diathermy method. Many international studies are available as well as limited local data regarding this topic. Global studies are in favor of coblation method as compared to diathermy method in terms of blood loss, pain and post operative complications.^{7,9} This study will help to generate data from local population. If this study proves coblation as good procedure as compared to bipolar electrocautery methods then in future we will be able to better manage our pediatric patients for tonsillectomies and improve post operative results.¹⁰

METHODOLOGY

This prospective comparative study was conducted at the Combined Military Hospital, Kharian Cantt, from 1st February 2023 to 31st January 2024 (IERB Certificate No. A/24/31 dated 14th December 2022). The sample size was calculated to be 60 patients, using the EPI sample size calculator with a 95% confidence interval and 5% margin of error, based on a previous study by Kiran et al. with a similar population and sample size.¹¹ The independent sample t-test was applied for comparison.

A total of 60 pediatric patients were selected through simple random sampling and divided equally into two groups:

- **Group A:** Coblation tonsillectomy (n = 30)
- **Group B:** Bipolar electrocautery tonsillectomy (n = 30)

All surgeries in **Group A** were performed by the same consultant, and all surgeries in **Group B** were performed by another consultant, both having more than **five years of post-graduate surgical experience**. No preoperative medication was administered. **Postoperative analgesia** was provided using **Paracetamol infusion only**.¹⁰

Inclusion Criteria

Children aged **4–15 years**, of either gender, with **recurrent tonsillitis** were included.¹² Patients with **chronic tonsillitis** and **tonsillar infections not relieved by adequate medical therapy** were also included.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients with **acute infections**, **severe systemic illnesses**, or **bleeding disorders** were excluded after thorough clinical examination and relevant laboratory investigations.¹³

Procedure

After obtaining **written and verbal informed consent** from guardians, detailed **history, examination, and assessment** were performed. In **Group A**, tonsillectomy was performed using **Coblation (radiofrequency energy)**, while **Group B** underwent **Bipolar Electrocautery (electrical energy)** tonsillectomy. Both techniques were performed under **general anesthesia** using standard dissection procedures. The anesthesia protocol was identical in both groups. Patients were closely monitored for **postoperative complications**. The **Wong–Baker FACES Pain Rating Scale** was provided for daily pain assessment.¹⁴ All patients had an equal **hospital stay duration, discharge timing, and follow-up intervals** in the ENT outpatient department.

Intraoperative Observations

During surgery, care was taken to protect the **pharyngeal mucosa**. Occasional bleeding points were secured using **bipolar diathermy**. The

coagulation technique was effective in achieving complete hemostasis.^{3, 8}

Both techniques were evaluated for **operative time**, defined as the interval from the first incision to the achievement of hemostasis of the tonsillar bed.^{9, 11, 14}

Intraoperative blood loss was measured by calculating the total fluid collected in the suction bottle, subtracting the volume of saline used during the procedure.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using **SPSS version 29.0**. **Mean ± SD** was calculated for continuous variables, and **frequencies (%)** for categorical variables. The **independent sample t-test** was used for comparison, with a **p-value < 0.05** considered statistically significant.

Normality was assessed using the **Shapiro–Wilk test**. Variables such as Mean Operative Time (Group A), Complications (Group A), and Mean Blood Loss (Group B) were normally distributed ($p > 0.05$). Conversely, Gender (Group A and B), Mean Operative Time (Group B), Pain Score (Group A and B), Complications (Group B), and Mean Blood Loss (Group A) deviated significantly from normality ($p < 0.05$). This guided the choice of appropriate statistical tests, ensuring the validity of the analysis.

Results:

A total of **60 children** were included in the study, comprising **33 males (55%)** and **27 females (45%)**, with ages ranging from **4 to 15 years**. Group A (Coblation tonsillectomy) included **63.3% males**, while Group B (Bipolar Electrocautery tonsillectomy) had **46.7% males**.

Operative Time and Intraoperative Blood Loss

The mean operative time and intraoperative blood loss for both groups are presented in **Table-I**. Bipolar Electrocautery tonsillectomy demonstrated a significantly **shorter operative time** compared to Coblation tonsillectomy ($p < 0.05$). Although mean blood loss was slightly lower in the Coblation group, this difference was **not statistically significant**.

Table-I: Mean operative time and intraoperative blood loss

	Group A (Coblation)	Group B (Bipolar Electrocautery)
Mean Operative Time	20.78 ± 1.14 min	15.45 ± 0.48 min
Mean Blood Loss	6.48 ± 0.67 ml	7.47 ± 0.42 ml

Postoperative Pain

Postoperative pain was assessed using the **Wong-Baker FACES Pain Rating Scale** (Figure-1). Mean postoperative pain scores were **significantly**

lower in the Coblation group compared to the Bipolar Electrocautery group (**p < 0.05**), as shown in **Table-II**.

Table II: Mean postoperative pain scores (Wong-Baker FACES)

Group A	Mean ± SD
Group A (Coblation)	2.90 ± 0.76
Group B (Bipolar Electrocautery)	3.83 ± 0.95

Coblation tonsillectomy resulted in **significantly lower postoperative pain** compared to Bipolar Electrocautery (**p < 0.05**).

Figure 1: Wong-Baker FACES pain score used for data collection

Postoperative Hemorrhagic Complications

Postoperative hemorrhagic complications are summarized in **Table-III**. No patient in the Coblation group developed postoperative hemorrhage, whereas **two patients (6.7%)** in the Bipolar Electrocautery group experienced

secondary hemorrhage on the eighth postoperative day. Local application of **hydrogen peroxide** achieved hemostasis after clot removal.^{15,17}

Table III: Postoperative haemorrhagic complications

Complications	Group A	Group B
Hemorrhage	00 (0.0% ± 0.0)	02 (6.7% ± 0.25)

Discussion:

A comparative study was done regarding the evaluation of two types of tonsillectomies. Out of 60 children, 33 were male and 27 were female.

The mean age of patients ranged from 4-15 years. Coblation and Bipolar electrocautery tonsillectomy both techniques appeared beneficial to treat tonsillitis in children or many

other problems associated with the nose and throat.^{4,5,18} Total tonsillectomies were done via both techniques. The patients with different indications for the surgery were selected for the study.^{18,19} Although both surgical techniques have their own pros and cons, however, these two techniques have different perspectives regarding removing the tonsils.^{9,11} It is noted that coblation tonsillectomy uses radiofrequency energy around 40 to 60 C to remove tonsils while on the other hand, bipolar electrocautery tonsillectomy uses electrical energy of above 300 C to remove tonsils.¹⁹

The comparison of Coblation and Bipolar electrocautery tonsillectomy highlights important considerations for choosing the appropriate technique for pediatric patients. While both methods yielded similar outcomes in terms of intraoperative blood loss, Bipolar electrocautery tonsillectomy had less mean operative time duration. Considering the pediatric candidates under observation, Coblation emerged as the more favorable technique because it yielded less post-operative pain and fewer complications. This reduced pain is particularly crucial in the pediatric population, where comfort during recovery significantly impacts overall outcomes.^{9,12,16,20} Although Bipolar electrocautery is also effective, the increased post-operative pain and the potential for hemorrhage may necessitate a careful evaluation of patient needs and surgeon expertise when selecting a surgical approach.²¹

According to the comparative study, there are various factors that contribute in evaluation of both techniques of tonsillectomy.^{9,21} Duration of operation was different between coblation and bipolar electrocautery tonsillectomy from previous provided data in literature. Group A and Group B both were under observation for the sake of examination of various factors. It is seen that Coblation tonsillectomy is less painful as compared to bipolar electrocautery tonsillectomy using a subjective scoring technique. Patient of Group A also suffered from mean postoperative pain but Group B faced a slight greater degree of pain after 8 days of surgery.^{17,21} Meanwhile, it is also noted that there is no significant difference in blood loss during

Coblation tonsillectomy and Bipolar electrocautery tonsillectomy similar to previously provided data in literature.^{14,15}

Patients from both groups faced minimum and limited blood loss during surgery. It is observed that both types of tonsillectomies offer some similar parameters that allows comprehensive study about these two techniques.⁹ Although, both the techniques use different mechanisms of action through which tonsils are removed. It is to be noted for future reference that bipolar electrocautery tonsillectomy offered prolonged pain in comparison to coblation tonsillectomy for pediatric age group.²⁰ In children, post-operative pain is considered more important than any other factor. However, pain was described as subjective finding and was influenced by many factors in hospital and home stay. Post-operative complications like hemorrhage also related to bipolar electrocautery tonsillectomy. It is to be noted that haemorrhagic conditions are common during the surgery. There are several important mechanisms used to stop bleeding per-operatively, post operative techniques and management also varies if incidence of secondary hemorrhage occurs and removal of blood clots is required.^{15,18,21} Coblation tonsillectomy appeared to have less rate of post operative complications as compared to Bipolar electrocautery tonsillectomy. It was noted that patients of group B faced prolonged pain and secondary haemorrhagic points after the 8-9 days of surgery while the coblation tonsillectomy patients had comparatively decreased post operative pain with no episodes of secondary haemorrhage. Hydrogen peroxide or clot removing techniques were used to deal with haemorrhagic points.²² Application of hydrogen peroxide on bleeding point directly and manual removal of clot normalizes the blood flow.²² Both the techniques are beneficial for removing tonsils to cure diseases associated with sleep apnoea in children.¹⁸

The study has its limitations; the sample sizes used are small and data collected for pain scoring was subjective. Each group was allocated a different surgeon that performed all the surgeries in that respective group. Causes of secondary

haemorrhage can be attributed to multiple factors.

Conclusion:

It is concluded that Coblation and Bipolar electrocautery tonsillectomy offer similar data regarding intraoperative blood loss. The calculated duration of surgery/operation time slightly increased in Coblation technique. However, it is evident that Coblation technique offers less post-operative complications as compared to Bipolar electrocautery tonsillectomy. Similarly, Coblation causes less prolonged post-operative pain than bipolar. So, it is concluded that if there is no problem associated with availability, expertise and cost effectiveness, it is more advantageous to move forward with Coblation tonsillectomy for Pediatric age group.

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